

A Study on Maternal and Neonatal Outcome in Severe Preeclampsia**M. Srija¹, P. Nithya², Abinaya³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Annapoorna Medical College Hospital, Salem, Tamilnadu, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Annapoorna Medical College Hospital, Salem, Tamilnadu, India³Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Annapoorna Medical College Hospital, Salem, Tamilnadu, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Srija Manoharan

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Preeclampsia is best described as a pregnancy – specific syndrome that can affect virtually every organ system. Incidence of Preeclampsia is identified in 4 to 5% of all pregnancies. Hypertension in pregnancy is diagnosed, Preeclampsia is defined as increase in blood pressure, severe preeclampsia is characterized by the presence of evidence of multi organ involvement. The more profound the imminent signs and symptoms, the most likely that delivery will be required. This study has been conducted to study the effect of severe preeclampsia on pregnancy and maternal and neonatal outcome.

Aim of the Study: To study the prevalence of severe preeclampsia in relation to age, Parity and immunized. To study the incidence of various maternal complications and indications of preeclampsia, fetal outcome and complications, reduce the maternal mortality and morbidity.

Material and Methods: This is prospective observational study conducted at department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of a tertiary care hospital. It includes analysis of methods and indications of induction in severe preeclampsia, maternal and neonatal outcome in severe preeclampsia All patients with severe preeclampsia admitted in labour ward at our hospital who meet the below mentioned criteria were included in the study. Complete history taking, signs and symptoms of imminent eclampsia are noted. All patients required termination of pregnancy for various reasons. General condition of the patient was evaluated obstetric examination was carried out. PIH investigations were carried out

Results: Pre-eclampsia is more prevalent in both developed and developing countries contributing to maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. It will produce maternal syndrome. It includes Hypertension, proteinuria and with or without edema. Fetal syndrome includes foetal growth restriction, reduced amniotic fluid, and abnormal placentation.

Conclusion: Early booking and regular antenatal BP checkup and monitoring imminent symptoms plays a major role in reducing the complications of severe preeclampsia. Earlier detection of complication and proper management plays a key role in the management of severe preeclampsia. Termination of pregnancy should be considered in all cases of severe preeclampsia based on maternal and neonatal condition. The maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality was reduced significantly with effective management at all levels of health centers.

Keywords: Preeclampsia, Steriods, MgSO₄, IUGR, Blood Products, Abrupton etc.

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Introduction

Preeclampsia is best described as a pregnancy – specific syndrome that can affect virtually every organ system. Incidence of Preeclampsia is identified in 4 to 5% of all pregnancies.

Hypertensive disorders contributes greatly to maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality rates, together they are one of the deadly triad - along with hemorrhage and infection[5].

Hypertension in pregnancy is diagnosed empirically when appropriately taken blood pressure exceeds

140 mmHg systolic or 90 mmHg diastolic on two occasions at least 6 hours apart after 20 weeks of gestation. Preeclampsia is defined as increase in blood pressure along with new onset proteinuria, after 20 weeks of pregnancy. Severe preeclampsia is characterized by the presence of evidence of multi organ involvement may include thrombocytopenia, renal dysfunction, hepatocellular necrosis, central nervous system perturbations or pulmonary edema.

The more profound the imminent signs and symptoms, the most likely that delivery will be required.[1,2] This study has been conducted to study the effect of severe preeclampsia on pregnancy and maternal and neonatal outcome.

Aims of the Study

1. To study the prevalence of severe preeclampsia in relation to
 - Age
 - Parity
 - Booked or unbooked
2. To study the incidence of various maternal complications.
3. To study the method and indications for induction in severe preeclampsia,
4. To study the fetal outcome in pregnancies complicated by preeclampsia.[6]
5. The overall aim of the study is to reduce the maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality.

Materials and Methods

Methods: This is prospective observational study conducted from January 2024 to July 2024 in labour ward. It includes analysis of methods and indications of induction in severe preeclampsia, maternal and neonatal outcome in severe preeclampsia [1].

All patients with severe preeclampsia admitted in labour ward at our hospital who meet the below mentioned criteria were included in the study. Complete history taking, signs and symptoms of imminent eclampsia are noted.

All patients required termination of pregnancy for various reason.[6&7] General condition of the patient was evaluated obstetric examination was carried out. PIH investigations were carried out [2].

Ultrasound examination, fundus examination, fetal Doppler, is noted. Administration of corticosteroid history was noted. Mode of induction and delivery depends on gestational age and bishop’s score and urgency of termination. Fetal outcome assessed by APGAR score at birth.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Gestational age > 20 weeks, irrespective of parity.
- Systolic BP: > 160 mmHg.
- Diastolic BP > 110 mmHg
- Proteinuria >= 3+ With any of the following
- Persistent headache
- Blurred vision
- Eclampsia
- Elevated liver enzymes
- Low platelets
- Abruptio placenta
- Oligohydramnios
- IUGR

Exclusion Criteria:

- Gestational age < 20 weeks
- Preexisting chronic renal and hepatic disorders
- Idiopathic haemolyticanaemia
- Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura
- Epilepsy.

Results and Analysis

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age In Years	No of Patients	Percentage
< 20 Years	46	23%
21-30 Years	134	67%
> 30 Years	20	10%

In our study group most of the women were in the age group between 21 – 30 yrs (67 %). Mean age group was 27 yrs. [Table-1]

Figure 1: Age Distribution

Table 2: Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic Status	No Of Patients	Percentage
I	0	0%
II	14	7%
III	153	76.50%
IV	32	16%
V	1	0.50%

Most of the women belonged to class 3 and 4 socio economic status. [Table-2]

Figure 2: Socioeconomic Status

Table 3: Body Mass Index

Body Mass Index	No of Patients	Percentage
18.5-25	77	38.50%
25-30	85	42.50%
30-35	38	19%

In our study 42.5% were overweight. [Table-3]

Figure 3: Body Mass Index

Table 4: Obstetric Score

Obstetric Score	No Of Patients	Percentage
PRIMI	103	52.50%
MULTI	97	48.50%

In our study group, primi and multi gravida shares equal incidence. [Table-4]

Figure 4: Obstetric Score

Table 5: Booking Status

Booking Status	No Of Patients	Percentage
Done	182	91%
Not Done	18	9%

In this study, 91% were booked and 9% were unbooked [Table-5]

Figure 5: Booking Status

Table 6: Gestational Age

Gestational Age	No of Patients	Percentage
20-28 Weeks	8	4%
28-32 Weeks	19	9.50%
32-36 Weeks	56	28%
> 36 Weeks	117	58.50%

In our study, 58.50% of patients were above 36 weeks of gestation. [Table-6]

Figure 6: Gestational Age

Table 7: Mode of Delivery

Mode of Delivery	No of Patients	Percentage
Labour Naturals	76	38%
LSCS	124	62%

In our study, 38% of patients were Labour Naturals. [Table-7]

Figure 7: Mode of delivery

Table 8: Indication for LSCS

Indication For LSCS	No of Patients	Percentage
Maternal	90	73%
Fetal	34	27%

Figure 8: Indication for LSCS

In our study, 62% were delivered by caesarean section, among them 73% were maternal indication and 27 % were fetal indication. 38 % delivered by labour natural [Table-8]

Table 9: Presenting Illness

Presenting Illness	No of Patients	Percentage
Head Ache	110	55%
Blurring Of Vision	20	10%
Vomiting	35	17.50%
Epilepsy	13	6.50%
Others	22	11%

In this study, 55% complained of headache followed by vomiting (17.5%) and blurring of vision (10%).[Table-9]

Figure 9: Presenting illness

Table 10: Maternal Death

Maternal Death	No of Patients	Percentage
Present	0	0%
Absent	200	100%

There was no maternal mortality in our study [Table-10].

Figure 10: Maternal Death

Discussion

Pre-eclampsia is more prevalent in both developed and developing countries contributing to maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. It will produce maternal syndrome. It includes Hypertension, proteinuria and with or without edema. Fetal syndrome includes foetal growth restriction, reduced amniotic fluid, and abnormal placentation.

Age of Incidence: In our study most common age was 21-30, Sixty seven (67%) of the women in the study group were in the age group of 21 to 30 years, which correlates with the studies of Moodley in which the mean age was 26 years. In studies done by Brown MA and Buddle ML, D.R. Hall the mean age was 26 years. In our study mean age was 27 years. Similar incidence was found in SIBAI BH IN 1997. Least incidence was found in age group above 30 years. It positively correlates with Vitthal Kulchake study in 2010.

Socioeconomic Status: Most of the women, 153 (56.7%) and 32 (42.6%) belonged to socioeconomic class III and IV respectively. Low maternal socioeconomic status is a strong risk factor for preeclampsia.

In a study done by Lindsay et al they adjusted for the confounding effects of age, gravidity and multiple pregnancy, women with low socioeconomic status were more likely to develop preeclampsia (odds ratio 5.12; 95%) than women with high socio. After additional adjustment for

financial difficulties, smoking in pregnancy, working conditions, body mass index and blood pressure at enrollment, the odds ratio was 4.91).

BMI: In our study more than half of mothers were obese (19%) or over weight (42.5%), Some studies have referred to obesity as a risk factor for preeclampsia and showed that the relationship between maternal weight and preeclampsia is a progressive risk and varies from 4.3% in women with a BMI < 19.8 Kg/m², up to 13.3% for women with a BMI ≥ 35 kg/m² [12]. In a study by Vahid Roodsari et al. BMI was reported to be 24 kg/m² in the pre-pregnancy control group, 26.124 kg/m² in the gestational hypertension group, 26.24 kg/m² in the group with mild preeclampsia and 26.24 kg/m² in the severe preeclampsia group. It has been reported, according to the obtained results, that if weight increases before pregnancy, weight loss will prevent mortality during pregnancy. Jang et al. in Seoul, Korea, compared two groups and showed that the incidence of preeclampsia in women with overweight women is higher than those of normal weight.

Parity: In our study population there was equal incidence of severe pre eclampsia in both primi (52.5%) and multi gravida, Pre-eclampsia has been dubbed as 'a disease of primiparity'. However, the effects and mechanisms of the association of primiparity with pre-eclampsia have not been clearly defined. Variably (1.4-5.5 times) higher risks of pre-eclampsia were observed in primiparous women in all studies, with a summary

odds ratio (OR) of 2.42 [95% CI 2.16, 2.71]. The adjusted ORs were larger than crude ORs in all but one study after various adjustments. There has been a scarcity of studies examining any immune maladaptation parameters among primiparous vs. multiparous women, probably owing to technical limitations – the lack of useful and easy-to-measure indicators of immune tolerance at the maternal–fetal interface during pregnancy. Brown MA and Buddle ML33 said preeclampsia is predominant in nulliparous.

Booked Status: In our study almost 91% of patients were booked early in their pregnancy, Adequate antenatal care has an important role in reducing the complications by early detection and appropriate management

Gestational Age: Coming to gestational age in our study, around 58.5% of patients were above 36 weeks followed by 28% of patients between 32-36 weeks, There was a positive correlation between gestational age at diagnosis and the Fetal outcome. Earlier the onset of preeclampsia greater is the fetal complications, 95.2% at 24 to 28 weeks compared to 43.4% after 32 weeks.

Past History: In our study history of eclampsia was present in 49(24.50%) mothers, and family history was present in 18 mothers (9%). A meta-analysis done showed that for multiparous women, the risk was significantly different for women who had pre-eclampsia in one (around 15%) or two (around 30%) consecutive previous pregnancies than for those with no history (around 1%). Although a longer interval between first and second pregnancies was associated with a higher incidence of pre-eclampsia, the risk for women without pre-eclampsia during their first pregnancy remained substantially lower even after eight years (2.2%), compared with women with pre-eclampsia in their first pregnancy [8]

Delivery: In our study, 109 mothers required induction either by foleys (n=78) or gel (n=31), most common cause of induction being maternal (n=80) followed by fetal (n=29), Maternal indication for induction was uncontrolled Blood pressure (62%), Abruption (16%) and oligohydramnios (22%) [4]. IUGR is the most common fetal indication for induction. Prompt delivery of the baby, preferably by vaginal route, is vital in order to achieve good maternal and neonatal outcomes. Induction of labour is therefore a critical intervention in order to prevent morbidity to both mother and baby. In a study done by Kaur et al in Punjab it concluded that there is no difference in efficacy between intracervical Foley's catheter and intracervical PGE2 gel for induction of labour. Also, other factors like induction delivery interval, maternal and neonatal outcomes were

similar in both the groups. Both methods are complementary to each other.

The most common mode of delivery is caesarean section (62%) and rest was by labour natural(38%), maternal cause is most common indication(n=90) followed by fetal indication(n=34) like respiratory distress, According to the guideline, [9,10] preeclampsia is not an indication of caesarean section expect with some serious complication. It means that pregnant women with preeclampsia can have a vaginal trial. However, it's report that the caesarean section rate of preeclampsia was significantly higher than normal pregnant women There are two reason why caesarean rate is higher, one is patient choose caesarean to avoid suffering, another is patients who underwent vaginal trial gets end up in caesarean for some reason. This LSCS rate in our study is higher than that reported by Mashiloane and Moodley but similar to that of Hall et al where 81.5% delivered by means of caesarean section.

Complications: Among our study population of 200 mothers with severe preeclampsia, 20 mothers had developed seizures (progression to stage of eclampsia). It can cause dangerous complications for the mother and the fetus. One of these complications is eclampsia, the term used when seizures develop in a woman with severe preeclampsia.

Abruption was seen in 31 mothers in our study, Although severe preeclampsia is a strong risk factor for placental abruption, transient hypertension in pregnancy and mild preeclampsia have also been linked to placental abruption in some , but not all studies. However, variable criteria have been used to define preeclampsia. The risk for abruption is further increased among women with hypertensive disorder who are exposed to passive or active smoking.

Pulmonary oedema is infrequent in severe preeclampsia-eclampsia without associated medical, surgical and obstetric complications. The occurrence of pulmonary oedema in such patients is associated with high maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity. In our study 12 mothers developed pulmonary oedema,

Coming to other maternal complication, atonic PPH developed in 40 mothers, DIC in 11 mothers. Atonic PPH was treated with blood transfusion in 15 mothers and uterotonics in all of them. Fresh frozen plasma was also administered in mothers who developed DIC. Women with pre-eclampsia have a 1.53-fold increased risk for postpartum haemorrhage. Clinicians should be aware of this, considering the complexity of PE with vascular changes and haemoconcentration in conjunction with the consequences of PPH leading to transfusion, embolization or surgery, a combination

of these two conditions forms a strong indication for a multidisciplinary approach, consisting of obstetric, anaesthetic, radiological and internal support.

Few studies reported higher rates of wound infection and endometritis in women with preeclampsia undergoing cesarean delivery. Possible causes of this association have been argued: immunosuppression, micronutrient deficiency, hyperalbuminaemia and the presence of ischemic tissue due to the vasospasm present in patients suffering from PIH. On the other hand, suffering from preeclampsia are more frequently submitted to caesarean which in itself increases the risk of infection. In our study 20 mothers had wound infection

Due to proper approach to management protocol and rigorous treatment, there was no maternal mortality in our study, Women with preeclampsia and eclampsia had a 3- to 25-fold increased risk of severe complications, such as abruptio placentae, thrombocytopenia, disseminated intravascular coagulation, pulmonary edema, and aspiration pneumonia. Hence due care should be given to avoid maternal mortality. In study conducted by Manisha et al in New Delhi in 2012 reported maternal mortality of 1.8% in their study.

Neonatal Outcome: Coming to the neonatal outcome, we evaluated APGAR score at one minute and five minutes. At 1 minute 55 babies had reduced apgar score and at 5 minute 35 babies had reduced APGAR score. The neonatal outcome depends on the intensive care facilities and the gestational age at birth. Within et al⁹⁴ reported that neonatal outcome in early onset severe preeclampsia was directly correlating with increasing birth weight and respiratory distress syndrome reduced with increasing gestational age.

IUGR was seen in 8 babies, IUD in 30 babies and neonatal death in 11 babies. NICU Admission required in 106 babies for one or other complications. Severe preeclampsia represents significant risk factor for intrauterine fetal demise, with estimated stillbirth rate of 21 per 1000. In the setting of severe preeclampsia, as previously discussed, the risk of fetal death outweighs the potential benefits of pregnancy prolongation. However, in cases of mild preeclampsia, the risk of fetal demise is over 50% less than pregnancies with severe preeclampsia. Ødegård et al. showed pregnancies complicated by severe preeclampsia had infant birth weights 12% lower than expected, while pregnancies with mild preeclampsia showed no difference in weight gain from expected norms. In the study by Ndaboine et al perinatal mortality was 20.7% (stillbirths 12.2% and neonatal death 8.5%), in the study by Mahram et al, it was 38.6% (stillbirths 2.7% and neonatal death 9.5%%). There

were (54%) NICU admissions in our study and in the study conducted by Lee et al there were 59% NICU admissions while in the study conducted by Mahran et al 18.8%.

Postpartum Period: Post-partum blood pressure control in mothers was achieved mostly within 3 days (n=132) and in 66 mothers in a week, only for two mothers it took more than a week. Similarly, hospital stay 69 mothers required less than a week stay, 111 mothers required 7-14 days stay. Prolonged hospitalisation in most of the women was for baby's sake. In the study by D.R. Hall¹⁴ mean period of postpartum hospitalisation was 5 days.

Summary

- In our study, 200 severe preeclampsia cases were taken.
- Most common age group in our study was 21 – 30 years; with mean age was 26years.
- Most of the women belonged to class 3 and 4 socio economic status
- In our study, 42.5% of patients were overweight and 19% were obese
- In our study population, incidence was equally distributed among primi and multigravida.
- Most of the women were booked (91%)
- Most common gestational age at presentation in our study was 36 weeks (58.5%)
- 55% of patients had headache as the presenting complaints
- Family history was present in 9%
- Most common indication for termination was maternal (n= 80)
- Most common mode of delivery is caesarean section (62%), labour natural (38%)
- Only 10% developed eclampsia in our study
- 62% were admitted in NICU, 75% were alive and healthy, 25% were IUD.
- IN 66% of patients, BP normalizes within 3 days.

Conclusion

Early booking and regular antenatal BP checkup and monitoring imminent symptoms plays a major role in reducing the complications of severe preeclampsia Earlier detection of complication and proper management plays a key role in the management of severe preeclampsia. Termination of pregnancy should be considered in all cases of severe preeclampsia based on maternal and neonatal condition.

The maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality was reduced significantly with effective management at all levels of health centers.

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